

r2 for GY15

Additional file 7 (.pdf):

Figure S7: QTL limits obtained by the *LD_Adj* approach projected on heatmaps representing the level of LD between associated SNPs for each trait (DTA: male flowering time, plantHT: plant height and GY: grain yield) for each chromosome. Upper and lower triangles on the heatmaps represent the r^2 and r^2_K values between associated SNPs, respectively. Linkage disequilibrium between loci was colored according to values from weak LD (yellow) to high LD (red). The significant markers were ordered according to their physical positions on the chromosome and were represented by ticks on the four sides of the heatmaps. Limits of QTLs were displayed by gray dotted lines. QTL numbers were indicated in gray on the top and the right of each heatmap.